

IN EDUCATION INNOVATION TECHNOLOGIES APPLICATION OF "RESUME" TECHNOLOGY IN ENTOMOLOGY LESSONS.

Komolidin Ganiyev Xalilovich

Ferghana State University, Uzbekistan

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Annotation

The article describes the importance of using problem situations in entomology lessons, methods and rules for creating problem situations and the use of innovative technologies in the study of insects. The importance of innovative technologies in education is described, which creates new opportunities for learning and the emergence of opportunities for personalizing learning, expanding communication opportunities and creating a more productive environment for learning entomology. It describes regular and systematic work on training, providing instant access to the necessary information and fostering important skills in working with sources, the ability to distinguish high-quality sources of information from unreliable, attracting young people to scientific activities, the formation of an innovative infrastructure of science in higher educational institutions.

Keywords: Educational objectives, spiritual and intellectual potential of society, world pedagogical experience, modern pedagogical technologies, path of independent development, positive and negative outlook on the world, advantages and disadvantages, process, methodology, innovation, creative thought, creative approach.

The future of each society is determined by how developed the education system is, which is an integral part of it and a vital necessity. As you know, the continuity and continuity of education, limiting excessive repetition in the system, expands, first of all, the spiritual and intellectual potential of society, and also ensures the sustainable development of production as a factor in improving the social and scientific and technological progress of the state.

In the process of developing pedagogical technologies and their introduction into the educational process, as well as the rapid exchange and improvement of information technologies, an opportunity is created for each person to strengthen their professional training and skills. Reforming and improving the system of continuing education in our country, which today is on the path of independent development, bringing it to a new qualitative level, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies into it, improving the effectiveness of education have raised the level of state policy.[1,2]

The general pedagogical and didactic requirement for all levels of training is to increase the effectiveness of the student's independent work based on program knowledge, imagination and skills, increase interest in scientific thinking, academic discipline, deepen professional knowledge, increase their activity during theoretical and practical training. The world pedagogical experience confirms that the possibilities of modern pedagogical technologies to interest students in subjects, to increase their activity in independent work are limitless.[3,4]

Today's task of education is to teach students to function independently in an increasing information and educational environment, to use information flows rationally. To do this, it is necessary to provide them with the opportunity and conditions for uninterrupted independent work.

Insect infestation began in ancient times. These included bulsa, which was originally considered a food product, and then, when cattle breeding and agriculture were burned on the road, they began to be beaten as pests. At the same time it became known that among them there are useful insects. As a result, sericulture and beekeeping emerged, which became branches of entomological science. But the scientific processing of insects began in the XVII century.[5,6,7]

Today, entomological science and its branches face such important tasks as the theoretical and practical solution of such important issues as the protection of nature from pests, the conservation and wider use of useful insect species.[8]

Innovative technologies in the study of entomology, the use of "resume" technology in entomology lessons is as follows. First of all, let's give a description of this technology. This technology is complex, multidisciplinary, aimed at studying as many problematic topics as possible.

The essence of the technology is that it provides information on various branches of the subject at a time. Meanwhile, each of them is discussed from different points of view.

The purpose of the technology is to make students think freely, independently, critically, work in a team, explore, find a solution to an educational problem based on a topic using the method of generalized comparison of opinions, as well as make the necessary conclusions or decisions, influence the team with their opinion, approve it, and also use the knowledge gained from the passed thus, when solving this problem, giving a general understanding of the subject, teach to apply their knowledge.

The technology can be used in lectures, seminars, practical and laboratory classes conducted individually or in small groups, as well as when doing homework. [9,10]

Tools used in entomology lessons, when studying the external structure of insects – a video clip, a handout made on A-3 paper, colored markers, depending on the number of groups.

The application of the technology is carried out in order:

- the teacher divides the students into subgroups of 3-5 people depending on their number;
- the teacher introduces students to the purpose and procedure of the lesson, and sets each subgroup a task that has an inscription at the top of the sheet, i.e. the main problem, from which he distributes divided learning tasks and ways to solve them with a written conclusion;
- preference for tasks on the sheets that the members of each group fall on, and identifying shortcomings, they express their thoughts in writing using various markers. Based on the opinions expressed in writing, they find a solution to this problem and make a general conclusion about the most acceptable option;[11,12,13]
- one of the members of the small group presents the prepared material on behalf of the team. The thoughts expressed by the group in writing are read out, but not introduced into the final part;
- the teacher asks the other subgroups for the conclusion of the group in which he made the presentation and determines their opinion, after the opinion of the groups, the presentation group presents its conclusion;
- the teacher comments on the opinions or conclusions made by the groups, evaluates them, and then completes the training.[14,15,16,17]

Based on the above, students' knowledge is controlled as follows.

In writing	Advantages	
	Disadvantages	
Verbally	Advantages	
	Disadvantages	
Test	Advantages	
	Disadvantages	
At a distance	Advantages	
	Disadvantages	

New pedagogical technologies can be used in the process of teaching students the "resume" technology during trainings, open discussions, organization of individual, pair, small group and team work. In addition, the educational process presents samples of methods of conducting educational classes using pedagogical technologies, methods of introducing and analyzing the lesson, as well as conducting various educational classes held in educational institutions. The methodology of the educational process conducted using the "resume" technology can be changed by each teacher depending on the content, purpose, as well as the conditions of the taught subject and subject, the capabilities and needs of students, or on the basis of the technologies presented in the learning process to create and use their own proprietary technologies.

References:

1. Ишмухамедов Р., Абдуқодиров А., Пардаев А. “Таълимда инновацион технологиялар” (таълим муассасалари педагог-ўқитувчилари учун амалий тавсиялар) Тошкент 2008.
2. Khalilovich G. K. et al. Eriosoma Lanigerum Hausm Juice Damage Properties And Effects Of Entomophagy Against It //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2022. – Т. 7. – С. 78-84.
3. Mirzakhililovich Y. M., Nabibullaevich K. F., Abdulazizovna K. B. Ecological geographical distribution of aphids (homoptera aphidinea, aphididae) in the fergana valley. – 2021.
4. Kizi M. I. B., Khasanbaevna R. D., Abdulazizovna K. B. Use and protection of water resources in uzbekistan: current state and development PATHS //Достижения науки и образования. – 2021. – №. 3 (75). – С. 10-12.
5. Xalilovich, G. K., Mamatyusufog'li, M. A., Abdulazizovna, X. B., Maxammadzikirovna, G. O., & Tursunaliyevna, T. M. (2021). “The Impact of Environmental Pollution on The Variability Of Fruit Gardens And Soilkomomokomplexes (Fergana-Margilan-Quvasoy Industrial Node)”. Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business & Government, 27(4).
6. Barnogul K., Khilola T. The essence of the biological education process, teaching printouts and legislation //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 4. – С. 129-133.
7. Abdulazizovna, K. B. (2022). Impact of environmental pollution on soil entomofauna on the example of the cities of fergana and kuvasay. Barqarorlik va yetakchi tadqiqotlar onlayn ilmiy jurnali, 2(12), 280-284.
8. Abdulazizovna, K. B. (2022). The use of interactive methods and innovative technologies in entomology lessons while studying insect morphology.

International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(09), 113-117.

9. Abdulazizovna, K. B., & Rustamjanovna, Z. N. (2022). Education and personality in the context of globalization. International journal of research in commerce, it, engineering and social sciences ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(09), 21-26.

10. Khalilova, B., & Abdurakhmonov, A. (2022). The need to develop environmental knowledge. Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities, 12(6), 119-124.

11. Abdulazizovna K. B. et al. Information technologies as a step to the development of society //international journal of research in commerce, it, engineering and social sciences ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 3. – C. 73-77.

12. Abdulazizovna K. B. et al. Timely implementation of personal education measures in the context of globalization //international journal of research in commerce, it, engineering and social sciences ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 3. – C. 87-92.

13. Abdulazizovna K. B. et al. The significance of mathematical knowledge in solving problems in biology //international journal of research in commerce, it, engineering and social sciences ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 3. – C. 93-99

14. Khalilova, B. A., & qizi Zuxriddinova, Z. N. (2023). IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION ON SOIL FAUNA (FERGANA-KUVASAY INDUSTRIAL NODE). YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS, 2(3), 5-12.

15. Камолиддин, Г. Х., & Барногул, А. Х. (2023, Май). РОЛЬ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ СТРУКТОРНОЙ ГЕНОМИКИ. In International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation (Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 32-40).

16. Khalilova, B. A. (2023). Didactic Foundations of Problem-Based Learning Technology in Teaching Entomology. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 2(4), 280-284.

17. Khalilova, B. A. (2023). "Problem Situations"-Methods and Rules of Creation, Use in Entomology Lessons. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 2(4), 275-279.

